

Single-Valued Neutrosophic Hyperrings and Single-Valued Neutrosophic Hyperideals

D. Preethi¹, S. Rajareega², J. Vimala^{3,*}, Ganeshsree Selvachandran⁴ and Florentin Smarandache⁵

^{1,2,3} Department of Mathematics, Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail: vimaljey@alagappauniversity.ac.in; reega948@gmail.com ; preethi06061996@gmail.com

⁴ Department of Actuarial Science and Applied Statistics, Faculty of Business and Information Science, UCSI University, Jalan Menara Gading, 56000 Cheras, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. E-mail: ganeshsree86@yahoo.com or Ganeshsree@ucsiuniversity.edu.my

⁵ Department of Mathematics, University of New Mexico, 705 Gurley Avenue, Gallup, NM 87301, New Mexico, USA.

E-mail: smarand@unm.edu

* Correspondence: J. Vimala (vimaljey@alagappauniversity.ac.in)

Abstract. In this paper, we introduced the concepts of Single-valued neutrosophic hyperring and Single-valued neutrosophic hyperideal. The algebraic properties and structural characteristics of the single-valued neutrosophic hyperrings and hyperideals are investigated and verified.

Keywords: Hyperring, Hyperideal, Single-valued neutrosophic set, Single-valued neutrosophic hyperring and Single-valued neutrosophic hyperideal.

1 Introduction

Hyperstructure theory was introduced by Marty in 1934 [16]. The concept of hyperring and the general form of hyperring for introducing the notion of hyperring homomorphism was developed by Corsini [11]. Vougiouklis [31] coined different type of hyperrings called H_v -ring, H_v -subring, and left and right H_v -ideal of a H_v -ring, all of which are generalizations of the corresponding concepts related to hyperrings introduced by Corsini [11].

In general fuzzy sets [34] the grade of membership is represented as a single real number in the interval $[0,1]$. The uncertainty in the grade of membership of the fuzzy set model was overcome using the interval-valued fuzzy set model introduced by Turksen [29]. In 1986, Atanassov [8] introduced intuitionistic fuzzy sets which is a generalization of fuzzy sets. This model was equivalent to interval valued fuzzy sets in [32]. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets can only handle incomplete information, and not indeterminate information which commonly exists in real-life [32]. To overcome these problems, Smarandache introduced the neutrosophic model. Some new trends of neutrosophic theory were introduced in [1,2,3,4,5,6,7]. Wang et al. [32] introduced the concept of single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNSs), whereas Smarandache introduced plithogenic set as generalization of neutrosophic set model in [13].

The theory of hyperstructures are widely used in various mathematical theories. The study on fuzzy algebra began by Rosenfeld [17], and this was subsequently expanded to other fuzzy based models such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets, fuzzy soft sets and vague soft sets. Some of the recent works related to fuzzy soft rings and ideal, vague soft groups, vague soft rings and vague soft ideals can be found in [21; 22; 23; 26, 27]. Research on fuzzy algebra led to the development of fuzzy hyperalgebraic theory. The concept of fuzzy ideals of a ring introduced by Liu [15]. The generalization of the fuzzy hyperideal introduced by Davvaz [12]. The concepts of fuzzy γ -ideal was then introduced by Bharathi

and Vimala [10], and the fuzzy γ -ideal was subsequently expanded in [33]. The hypergroup and hyperring theory for vague soft sets were developed by Selvachandran et al. in [18,19,20,24,25] In this paper we develop the theory of single-valued neutrosophic hyperrings and single-valued neutrosophic hyperideals to further contribute to the development of the body of knowledge in neutrosophic hyperalgebraic theory.

2 Preliminaries

Let X be a space of points (objects) with a generic element in X denoted by x .

Definition 2.1. [32] A SVN A is a neutrosophic set that is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$, where $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. This set A can thus be written as

$$A = \{x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) : x \in U\}. \quad (1)$$

The sum of $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ must fulfill the condition $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$. For a SVN A in U , the triplet $(T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x))$ is called a single-valued neutrosophic number (SVNN). Let $x = (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ to represent a SVNN.

Definition 2.2. [32] Let A and B be two SVN's over a universe U .

- (i) A is contained in B , if $T_A(x) \leq T_B(x), I_A(x) \leq I_B(x)$, and $F_A(x) \geq F_B(x)$, for all $x \in U$. This relationship is denoted as $A \subseteq B$.
- (ii) A and B are said to be equal if $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$.
- (iii) $A^c = (x, (F_A(x), 1 - I_A(x), T_A(x)))$, for all $x \in U$.
- (iv) $A \cup B = (x, (\max(T_A, T_B), \max(I_A, I_B), \min(F_A, F_B)))$, for all $x \in U$.
- (v) $A \cap B = (x, (\min(T_A, T_B), \min(I_A, I_B), \max(F_A, F_B)))$, for all $x \in U$.

Definition 2.3. [16] A hypergroup $\langle H, \circ \rangle$ is a set H with an associative hyperoperation $(\circ) : H \times H \rightarrow P(H)$ which satisfies $x \circ H = H \circ x = H$ for all x in H (reproduction axiom).

Definition 2.4.[12] A hyperstructure $\langle H, \circ \rangle$ is called an H_v -group if the following axioms hold:

- (i) $x \circ (y \circ z) \cap (x \circ y) \circ z \neq \emptyset$ for all $x, y, z \in H$, (H_v -semigroup)
- (ii) $x \circ H = H \circ x = H$ for all x in H .

Definition 2.5.[16] A subset K of H is called a *subhypergroup* if $\langle K, \circ \rangle$ is a hypergroup.

Definition 2.6.[11]A H_v -ring is a multi-valued system $(R, +, \circ)$ which satisfies the following axioms:

- (i) $(R, +)$ is a H_v -group,
- (ii) (R, \circ) is a H_v -semigroup,
- (iii) The hyperoperation " \circ " is weak distributive over the hyperoperation "+", that is for each $x, y, z \in R$ the conditions $x \circ (y + z) \cap ((x \circ y) + (x \circ z)) \neq \emptyset$ and $(x + y) \circ z \cap ((x \circ z) + (y \circ z)) \neq \emptyset$ holds true.

Definition 2.7. [11]A nonempty subset R' of R is a *subhyperring* of $(R, +, \circ)$ if $(R', +)$ is a subhypergroup of $(R, +)$ and for all $x, y, z \in R'$, $x \circ y \in P^*(R')$, where $P^*(R')$ is the set of all non-empty subsets of R' .

Definition 2.8. [11] Let R be a H_v -ring. A nonempty subset I of R is called a *left* (respectively *right*) H_v -ideal if the following axioms hold:

- (i) $(I, +)$ is a H_v -subgroup of $(R, +)$,
- (ii) $R \circ I \subseteq I$ (resp. $I \circ R \subseteq I$).

If I is both a left and right H_v -ideal of R , then I is said to be a H_v -ideal of R .

3 Single-Valued Neutrosophic Hyperrings

Throughout this section, we denote the hyperring $(R, +, \circ)$ by R .

Definition 3.1. Let A be a SVN over R . A is called a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R , if,

- (i) $\forall a, b \in R, \min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a + b\}, \max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_A(c) : c \in a + b\}$ and $\max\{F_A(a), F_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_A(c) : c \in a + b\}$
- (ii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $b \in R$ such that $a \in x + b$ and $\min\{T_A(x), T_A(a)\} \leq T_A(b), \max\{I_A(x), I_A(a)\} \geq I_A(b)$ and $\max\{F_A(x), F_A(a)\} \geq F_A(b)$
- (iii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $c \in R$ such that $a \in c + x$ and $\min\{T_A(x), T_A(a)\} \leq T_A(c), \max\{I_A(x), I_A(a)\} \geq I_A(c)$ and $\max\{F_A(x), F_A(a)\} \geq F_A(c)$
- (iv) $\forall a, b \in R, \min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a \circ b\}, \max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_A(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$ and $\max\{F_A(a), F_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_A(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$

Example 3.2. The family of t -level sets of SVN over R is a subhyperring of R is given below:

$$A_t = \{a \in R : T_A(a) \geq t, I_A(a) \leq t, F_A(a) \leq t\}, \text{ for all } t \in [0, 1].$$

Then A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R .

Theorem 3.3. A is a SVN over R . Then A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R iff A is single-valued neutrosophic semi hyper group over (R, \circ) and also a single-valued neutrosophic hypergroup over $(R, +)$.

Proof. This is obvious by Definition 3.1. ■

Theorem 3.4. Let A and B be single-valued neutrosophic hyperrings over R . Then $A \cap B$ is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R if it is non-null.

Proof. Let A and B are single-valued neutrosophic hyperrings over R . By Definition 3.1, $A \cap B = \{(a, T_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(a)) : a \in R\}$, where $T_{A \cap B}(a) = \min(T_A(a), T_B(a)), I_{A \cap B}(a) = \max(I_A(a), I_B(a)), F_{A \cap B}(a) = \max(F_A(a), F_B(a))$. Then for all $a, b \in R$, we have the following. We only prove all the four conditions for the truth membership terms T_A, T_B . The proof for the I_A, I_B and F_A, F_B membership functions obtained in a similar manner.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad \min\{T_{A \cap B}(a), T_{A \cap B}(b)\} &= \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_B(a)), \min(T_A(b), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_A(b)), \min(T_B(a), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min\{\inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a + b\}, \inf\{T_B(c) : c \in a + b\}\} \\ &\leq \inf\{\min(T_A(c), T_B(c)) : c \in a + b\} \\ &= \inf\{T_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a + b\} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\max\{I_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a + b\}$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a + b\}$.

(ii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $b \in R$ such that $a \in x + b$. Then it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{T_{A \cap B}(a), T_{A \cap B}(b)\} &= \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_B(a)), \min(T_A(b), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_A(b)), \min(T_B(a), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min(T_A(c), T_B(c)) \\ &= T_{A \cap B}(c) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\max\{I_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq I_{A \cap B}(c)$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq F_{A \cap B}(c)$.

(iii) It can be easily verified that $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $c \in R$ such that $a \in c + x$ & $\min\{T_{A \cap B}(x), T_{A \cap B}(a)\} \leq T_{A \cap B}(c), \max\{I_{A \cap B}(x), I_{A \cap B}(a)\} \geq I_{A \cap B}(c)$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(x), F_{A \cap B}(a)\} \geq F_{A \cap B}(c)$.

$$F_{A \cap B}(c).$$

(iv) $\forall a \in R, \min\{T_{A \cap B}(a), T_{A \cap B}(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a \circ b\}, \max\{I_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$.

Hence, $A \cap B$ is single-valued neutrosophichyperring over R . ■

Theorem 3.5. Let A be a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R . Then for every $t \in [0, 1], A_t \neq \emptyset$ is a subhyperring over R .

Proof. Let A be a single-valued neutrosophichyperring over R . $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, let $a, b \in A_t$. Then $T_A(a), T_A(b) \geq t, I_A(a), I_A(b) \leq t$ and $F_A(a), F_A(b) \leq t$. Since A is a single-valued neutrosophic sub hyper group of $(R, +)$, we have the following:

$$\inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a + b\} \geq \min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \geq \min\{t, t\} = t,$$

$$\sup\{I_A(c) : c \in a + b\} \leq t,$$

and

$$\sup\{F_A(c) : c \in a + b\} \leq t.$$

This implies that $c \in A_t$ and then for every $c \in a + b$, we obtain $a + b \subseteq A_t$. As such, for every $c \in A_t$, we obtain $c + A_t \subseteq A_t$. Now let $a, c \in A_t$. Then $T_A(a), T_A(c) \geq t, I_A(a), I_A(c) \leq t$ and $F_A(a), F_A(c) \leq t$.

A is a single-valued neutrosophic subhypergroup of $(R, +)$, there exists $b \in R$ such that $a \in c + b$ and $T_A(b) \geq \min(T_A(a), T_A(c)) \geq t, I_A(b) \leq \max(I_A(a), I_A(c)) \leq t, F_A(b) \leq \max(F_A(a), F_A(c)) \leq t$, and this implies that $b \in A_t$. Therefore, we obtain $A_t \subseteq c + A_t$. As such, we obtain $c + A_t = A_t$. As a result, A_t is a subhypergroup of $(R, +)$.

Let $a, b \in A_t$, then $T_A(a), T_A(b) \geq t, I_A(a), I_A(b) \leq t$ and $F_A(a), F_A(b) \leq t$. Since A is a single-valued neutrosophic subsemihypergroup of (R, \circ) , then for all $a, b \in R$, we have the following:

$$\inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a \circ b\} \geq \min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} = t,$$

$$\sup\{I_A(c) : c \in a \circ b\} \leq \max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} = t,$$

and

$$\sup\{F_A(c) : c \in a \circ b\} \leq \max\{F_A(a), F_A(b)\} = t.$$

This implies that $c \in A_t$ and consequently $a \circ b \in A_t$. Therefore, for every $a, b \in A_t$ we obtain $a \circ b \in P^*(R)$. Hence A_t is a subhyperring over R .

Theorem 3.6. Let A be a single-valued neutrosophic set over R . Then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R .
- (ii) $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, a non-empty A_t is a sub hyperring over R .

Proof.

(i) \Rightarrow (ii) $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, by Theorem 3.5, A_t is sub hyperring over R .

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Assume that A_t is a subhyperring over R . Let $a, b \in A_t$ and therefore $a + b \subseteq A_{t_0}$. Then for every $c \in a + b$ we have $T_A(c) \geq t_0, I_A(c) \leq t_0$ and $F_A(c) \leq t_0$, which implies that:

$$\min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a + b\},$$

$$\max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_A(c) : c \in a + b\},$$

and

$$\max(F_A(a), F_A(b)) \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a + b\}$$

Therefore, condition (i) of Definition 3.1 has been verified.

Next, let $x, a \in A_{t_1}$ for every $t_1 \in [0, 1]$ which means that there exists $b \in A_{t_1}$ such that $a \in x \circ b$. Since $b \in A_{t_1}$, we have $T_A(b) \geq t_1, I_A(b) \leq t_1$ and $F_A(b) \leq t_1$, and thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_A(b) &\geq t_1 = \min(T_A(a), T_A(c)), \\ I_A(b) &\leq t_1 = \max(I_A(a), I_A(c)), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$F_A(b) \leq t_1 = \max(F_A(a), F_A(c)).$$

Therefore, condition (ii) of Definition 3.1 has been verified. Compliance to condition (iii) of Definition 3.1 can be proven in a similar manner. Thus, A is a single-valued neutrosophic subhypergroup of $(R, +)$. Now since A_t is a subsemihypergroup of the semihypergroup (R, \circ) , we have the following. Let $a, b \in A_{t_2}$ and therefore we have $a \circ b \in A_{t_2}$. Thus for every $c \in a \circ b$, we obtain $T_A(c) \geq t_2, I_A(c) \leq t_2$ and $F_A(c) \leq t_2$, and therefore it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \min(T_A(a), T_A(b)) &\leq \inf\{T_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}, \\ \max(I_A(a), I_A(b)) &\geq \sup\{I_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\max(F_A(a), F_A(b)) \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a \circ b\},$$

which proves that condition (iv) of Definition 3.1 has been verified. Hence A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperring over R .

4 Single-Valued Neutrosophic Hyperideals

Definition 4.1. Let A be a SVNS over R . Then A is single-valued neutrosophic left (resp. right) hyperideal over R , if ,

- (i) $\forall a, b \in R, \min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_A(c): c \in a + b\}, \max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_A(c): c \in a + b\}$ and $\max\{F_A(a), F_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a + b\}$
- (ii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $b \in R$ such that $a \in x + b$ and $\min\{T_A(x), T_A(a)\} \leq T_A(b), \max\{I_A(x), I_A(a)\} \geq I_A(b)$ and $\max\{F_A(x), F_A(a)\} \geq F_A(b)$
- (iii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $c \in R$ such that $a \in c + x$ and $\min\{T_A(x), T_A(a)\} \leq T_A(c), \max\{I_A(x), I_A(a)\} \geq I_A(c)$ and $\max\{F_A(x), F_A(a)\} \geq F_A(c)$
- (iv) $\forall a, b \in R, T_A(b) \leq \inf\{T_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$ (resp. $T_A(a) \leq \inf\{T_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$), $I_A(b) \geq \sup\{I_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$ (resp. $I_A(a) \geq \sup\{I_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$) and $F_A(b) \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$ (resp. $F_A(a) \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$)

A is a single-valued neutrosophic left (resp. right) hyperideal of R . From conditions (i), (ii) and (iii) A is a single-valued neutrosophic subhypergroup of $(R, +)$.

Definition 4.2. Let A be a SVNS over R . Then A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyper ideal over R , if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $\forall a, b \in R, \min\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_A(c): c \in a + b\}, \max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_A(c): c \in a + b\}$ and $\max\{F_A(a), F_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a + b\}$
- (ii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $b \in R$ such that $a \in x + b$ and $\min\{T_A(x), T_A(a)\} \leq T_A(b), \max\{I_A(x), I_A(a)\} \geq I_A(b)$ and $\max\{F_A(x), F_A(a)\} \geq F_A(b)$
- (iii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $c \in R$ such that $a \in c + x$ and $\min\{T_A(x), T_A(a)\} \leq T_A(c), \max\{I_A(x), I_A(a)\} \geq I_A(c)$ and $\max\{F_A(x), F_A(a)\} \geq F_A(c)$
- (iv) $\forall a, b \in R, \max\{T_A(a), T_A(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}, \max\{I_A(a), I_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$ and $\max\{F_A(a), F_A(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_A(c): c \in a \circ b\}$

From conditions (i), (ii) and (iii) A is a single-valued neutrosophic sub hyper group of $(R, +)$. Condition (iv) indicate both single-valued neutrosophic left hyperideal and single-valued neutrosophic right hyperideal. Hence A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyper ideal of R .

Theorem 4.3. Let A be a non-null SVN over R . A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperideal over R iff A is a single-valued neutrosophic hyper group over $(R, +)$ and also A is both a single-valued neutrosophic left hyper ideal and a single-valued neutrosophic right hyper ideal of R .

Proof. This is straight forward by Definitions 4.1 and 4.2.

Theorem 4.4. Let A and B be two single-valued neutrosophic hyper ideals over R . Then $A \cap B$ is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperideal over R if it is non-null.

Proof. Let A and B are single-valued neutrosophic hyper ideals over R . By Definition 4.2, $A \cap B = \{(a, T_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(a)) : a \in R\}$, where $T_{A \cap B}(a) = \min(T_A(a), T_B(a))$, $I_{A \cap B}(a) = \max(I_A(a), I_B(a))$ and $F_{A \cap B}(a) = \max(F_A(a), F_B(a))$. Then $\forall a, b \in R$, we have the following. We only prove all the four conditions for the truth membership terms T_A, T_B . The proof for the I_A, I_B and F_A, F_B membership functions obtained in a similar manner.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad \min\{T_{A \cap B}(a), T_{A \cap B}(b)\} &= \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_B(a)), \min(T_A(b), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_A(b)), \min(T_B(a), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min\{\inf\{T_A(c) : c \in a + b\}, \inf\{T_B(c) : c \in a + b\}\} \\ &\leq \inf\{\min(T_A(c), T_B(c)) : c \in a + b\} \\ &= \inf\{T_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a + b\} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, it can be proven that $\max\{I_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a + b\}$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a + b\}$.

(ii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $b \in R$ such that $a \in x + b$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{T_{A \cap B}(a), T_{A \cap B}(b)\} &= \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_B(a)), \min(T_A(b), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min\{\min(T_A(a), T_A(b)), \min(T_B(a), T_B(b))\} \\ &\leq \min(T_A(c), T_B(c)) \\ &= T_{A \cap B}(c) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\max\{I_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq I_{A \cap B}(c)$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq F_{A \cap B}(c)$.

(iii) $\forall x, a \in R$, there exists $c \in R$ such that $a \in c + x$ and $\min\{T_{A \cap B}(x), T_{A \cap B}(a)\} \leq T_{A \cap B}(c)$, $\max\{I_{A \cap B}(x), I_{A \cap B}(a)\} \geq I_{A \cap B}(c)$ and $\max\{F_{A \cap B}(x), F_{A \cap B}(a)\} \geq F_{A \cap B}(c)$.

(iv) $\forall a \in R$, $\max\{T_{A \cap B}(a), T_{A \cap B}(b)\} \leq \inf\{T_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$, $\min\{I_{A \cap B}(a), I_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{I_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$ and $\min\{F_{A \cap B}(a), F_{A \cap B}(b)\} \geq \sup\{F_{A \cap B}(c) : c \in a \circ b\}$.

Hence, it is verified that $A \cap B$ is a single-valued neutrosophic hyperideal over R .

5. Conclusion

We developed hyperstructure for the SVN model through several hyperalgebraic structures such as hyperrings and hyperideals. The properties of these structures were studied and verified. The future work is on the development of hyperalgebraic theory for Plithogenic sets which is the generalization of neutrosophic set and also planned to develop some real life applications.

Acknowledgement

The article has been written with the joint financial support of RUSA-Phase 2.0 grant sanctioned vide letter No. F 24-51/2014-U, Policy (TN Multi-Gen), Dept. of Edn. Govt. of India, Dt. 09.10.2018, UGC-SAP

(DRS-I) vide letter No.F.510/8/DRS-I/2016(SAP-I) Dt. 23.08.2016, DST-PURSE 2nd Phase programme vide letter No. SR/PURSE Phase 2/38 (G) Dt. 21.02.2017 and DST (FST - level I) 657876570 vide letter No.SR/FIST/MSI/2018/17 Dt. 20.12.2018.

The fourth author would like to gratefully acknowledge the financial assistance received from the Ministry of Education, Malaysia under grant no. FRGS/1/2017/STG06/UCSI/03/1.

References

1. Abdel-Basset, M., Mohamed, R., Zaiied, A. E. N. H., & Smarandache, F. (2019). A Hybrid Plithogenic Decision Making Approach with Quality Function Deployment for Selecting Supply Chain Sustainability Metrics. *Symmetry*, 11(7), 903.
2. Abdel-Basset, M., Nabeeh, N. A., El-Ghareeb, H. A., & Aboelfetouh, A. (2019). Utilising neutrosophic theory to solve transition difficulties of IoT-based enterprises. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 1-21.
3. Nabeeh, N. A., Abdel-Basset, M., El-Ghareeb, H. A., & Aboelfetouh, A. (2019). Neutrosophic multi-criteria decision making approach for iot-based enterprises. *IEEE Access*, 7, 59559-59574.
4. Abdel-Baset, M., Chang, V., & Gamal, A. (2019). Evaluation of the green supply chain management practices: A novel neutrosophic approach. *Computers in Industry*, 108, 210-220.
5. Abdel-Basset, M., Saleh, M., Gamal, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). An approach of TOPSIS technique for-developing supplier selection with group decision making under type-2 neutrosophic number. *Applied Soft Computing*, 77, 438-452.
6. Abdel-Baset, M., Chang, V., Gamal, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). An integrated neutrosophic ANP and VIKOR method for achieving sustainable supplier selection: A case study in importing field. *Computers in Industry*, 106, 94-110.
7. Abdel-Basset, M., Manogaran, G., Gamal, A., & Smarandache, F. (2019). A group decision making framework based on neutrosophic TOPSIS approach for smart medical device selection. *Journal of medical systems*, 43(2), 38
8. K. Atanassov. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 20 (1986) 87-96.
9. Balasubramaniyan Elavarasan, F. Smarandache, Young Bae Jun, Neutrosophic ideals in semigroups, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 28, 2019, pp. 273-280.
10. P. Bharathi and J. Vimala. The role of fuzzy γ -ideals in a commutative γ -group. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 12(3) (2016) 2067-2074.
11. P. Corsini. Prolegomena of hypergroup theory. Aviani Editor, Tricesimo, Italy, 2nd edition, 1993.
12. B. Davvaz. On H_v -rings and fuzzy H_v -ideal. *Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics* 6(1) (1998) 33-42.
13. F. Smarandache. Plithogeny, plithogenic set, logic, probability, and statistics. Pons Publishing House, Brussels, Belgium, 141 p., 2017; arXiv.org (Cornell University).
14. S. Khademan, M. M. Zahedi, R. A. Borzooei, Y. B. Jun, Neutrosophic Hyper BCK- Ideals, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 27, 2019, pp. 201-217.
15. W. J. Liu. Fuzzy invariant subgroups and fuzzy ideals. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 8(2) (1982) 133-139.
16. F. Marty. Sur unegeneralisation de la notion de groupe. *Proceedings of the 8th Congress Mathematiciens Scandinaves, Stockholm, Sweden* (1934) 45-49.
17. A. Rosenfeld. Fuzzy groups. *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 35 (1971) 512-517.
18. G. Selvachandran and A. R. Salleh. Vague soft hypergroups and vague soft hypergroup homomorphism. *Advances in Fuzzy Systems 2014* (2014) 1-10.
19. G. Selvachandran and A. R. Salleh. Algebraic hyperstructures of vague soft sets associated with hyperrings and hyperideals. *The Scientific World Journal* 2015 (2015) 1-12.
20. G. Selvachandran. Introduction to the theory of soft hyperrings and soft hyperring homomorphism. *JP Journal of Algebra, Number Theory and Applications* 36(3) (2015) 279-294.
21. G. Selvachandran and A. R. Salleh. Fuzzy soft ideals based on fuzzy soft spaces. *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences* 99(3) (2016) 429-438.
22. G. Selvachandran and A. R. Salleh. Rings and ideals in a vague soft set setting. *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences* 99(2) (2016) 279-300.
23. G. Selvachandran and A. R. Salleh. On normalistic vague soft groups and normalistic vague soft group homomorphism. *Advances in Fuzzy Systems 2015* (2015) 1-8.
24. G. Selvachandran and A. R. Salleh. Fuzzy soft hyperrings and fuzzy soft hyperideals. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 11(2) (2015) 807-823.

25. G. Selvachandran and A.R. Salleh. Hypergroup theory applied to fuzzy soft sets. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 11(2) (2015) 825-835.
26. G. Selvachandran and A.R. Salleh. Vague soft rings and vague soft ideals. *International Journal of Algebra* 6(12) (2012) 557-572.
27. G. Selvachandran and A.R. Salleh. Idealistic vague soft rings and vague soft ring homomorphism. *International Journal of Mathematical Analysis* 6(26) (2012) 1275-1290.
28. F. Smarandache. *Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic probability, set and logic*. ProQuest Learning, Ann Arbor, Michigan, 1998.
29. I. Turksen. Interval valued fuzzy sets based on normal forms. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 20 (1986) 191-210.
30. T. Vougiouklis. *Hyperstructures and their representations*. Hadronic Press, Palm Harbor, Florida, USA, 1994.
31. T. Vougiouklis. A new class of hyperstructures. *Journal of Combination and Information Systems and Sciences* 20 (1995) 229-235.
32. H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y.Q. Zhang and R. Sunderraman. Single valued neutrosophic sets. *Multi-space Multistructure* 4 (2010) 410-413.
33. J. Vimala and J. Arockia Reeta. Ideal approach on lattice ordered fuzzy soft group and its application in selecting best mobile network coverage among travelling paths. *ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* 13(7)(2018) 2414-2421.
34. L.A. Zadeh. Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control* 8 (1965) 338-353.

Received: June 15, 2019. Accepted: October 08, 2019